

WATER ON THE MOON

A European science team is advancing the development of water extraction from lunar regolith (surface material).

LEADING IDEA

The development, integration and validation of lunar water extraction and purification technologies for in-situ propellant and consumables production is a key requirement for future space exploration.

LUWEX, a project funded under the EU's Horizon Europe framework programme has started with a kick-off meeting under the lead of the German Aerospace Centre, DLR. LUWEX stands for Lunar Water Extraction and the project is focussed on developing technologies to obtain purified water from moon rock.

Water is the driving force of all nature, Leonardo da Vinci said. Water is by far the most versatile and most needed resource for human space exploration. It is the key commodity in life support systems as well as for cryogenic chemical rocket propellants.

Mission costs are proportional to the amount of mass initially placed in orbit. As we advance deeper into space, the cost to support exploration missions with Earth-based resources increases with distances. More than 7.5 kg of propellant and vehicle mass are required to deliver each kilogram of payload to the lunar surface. The utilisation of available local resources is key to a sustainable human presence on the moon or Mars and beyond. Indications for the availability of local raw water ice trapped in the lunar and Martian soil provide the motivation and substantial interest in viable technical solutions for finding, extracting, purifying and utilizing in situ-water. Previous research activities regarding lunar water extraction were mostly performed as theoretical system studies, complemented by a few small-scale experiments.

Distribution of lunar water ice

The interdisciplinary LUWEX team coming from Germany, Austria, Poland and Italy is designing and testing a novel water extractor that will be able to process several kilograms of lunar regolith containing enough water ice to support a purification process downstream. The terrestrial demonstration system will operate under a similar low pressure and low temperature environment as on the moon.

To test the system in the laboratory, a mix from water ice particles and lunar regolith simulant will substitute for real lunar sand as is expected to be found in some craters at the lunar south polar region. By applying heat, the vaporizing water is extracted and collected. After liquefaction, the raw water is put through a purification process. The purified water is then ready for use in the form of propellant, for energy storage and for life support, or for a glass of Adam's ale from the moon.

PARTICIPANT ORGANISATIONS

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